

Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Copper with 4-Nitrosoresorcinol in Presence of Pyridine and Substituted Pyridines

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EXTRACTIVE-PHOTOMETRIC determination of various metals with pyridine bases-thiocyanate has been reported¹⁻⁷. We have undertaken a systematic programme to study the extraction behaviour of copper(II) with 4-nitrosoresorcinol in presence of pyridine and some of its methyl-substituted derivatives. Based on these studies, a few rapid and sensitive methods for the extraction and spectrophotometric determination of copper(II) have been developed. The substituted-pyridines used are α -picoline, β -picoline, γ -picoline and 2,4,6-collidine.

Experimental

A Shimadzu PR1 spectrophotometer was used for absorbance measurements. A ECL 051 digital pH meter was used to measure the acidities of the aqueous solutions.

A stock solution of copper(II) was prepared from $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and standardised⁸ and solution of lower concentration made by appropriate dilution. Chloroform (E. Merck), pyridine (B.D.H.), α -picoline (Riedel), β -picoline (B.D.H.), γ -picoline (Fluka) and 2,4,6-collidine (B.D.H.) were distilled before use. 4-Nitrosoresorcinol was prepared as reported⁹ and its ethanolic solution (1%) was used. KCl-HCl buffer was used for pH adjustment.

General procedure: An aliquot containing upto 100 μg of Cu^{2+} was mixed with 1% ethanolic

solution (0.2 ml) of 4-nitrosoresorcinol followed by addition of pyridine/ α -picoline/ β -picoline/ γ -picoline/2,4,6-collidine (0.5 ml). Buffer solution (pH 2; 5 ml) was then added and volume of the aqueous phase was made upto 10 ml with distilled water. The solution was then equilibrated with chloroform (10 ml) in a separating funnel for 1 min. The separated organic layer was poured over anhydrous sodium sulphate to remove retained water droplets. Finally, the absorbance of the organic extract was measured at the corresponding absorption maxima against a copper-free reagent blank, and the amount of copper(II) determined. To test the effect of diverse ions, the respective foreign ions were added to the system before addition of the reagents.

Results and Discussion

The optimum pH for extraction for copper was ascertained by extracting the mixed-ligand complexes in the pH range 1.0-11.0. In all the cases maximum absorbance was attained at pH 1.5-2.5. In a second consecutive operation within this pH range, the organic extract virtually showed no absorbance. This indicated that copper(II) was quantitatively extracted in this condition.

The spectra of the mixed-ligand complexes were recorded in the wavelength region 300-600 nm against the corresponding reagent blank. The copper complexes showed λ_{max} at 365-375 nm.

Different amounts of copper(II) were extracted as described in the general procedure. In all the cases, Beer's law was found to be valid over the concentration range 1-10 ppm of copper. The Ringbom's optimum concentration range for measurement was found to be 3-10 ppm of copper(II). The corresponding molar absorptivity of the complexes (on the basis of copper content) and the respective Sandell's sensitivity values are shown in Table 1.

The optimum concentration of the reagents for extraction of copper(II) has been ascertained. It has been found that 0.2 ml of 1% ethanolic solution of 4-nitrosoresorcinol along with pyridine/ α -picoline/

TABLE 1 - DETAILS OF EXTRACTIVE METHODS

Parameter	Base employed				
	Pyridine	α -Picoline	β -Picoline	γ -Picoline	2,4,6-Collidine
pH	1.5-2.5	1.5-2.5	1.5-2.5	1.5-2.5	1.5-2.5
λ_{max} (nm)	365	375	370	370	365
Molar absorptivity ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	0.71×10^4	0.45×10^4	0.89×10^4	1.06×10^4	0.21×10^4
Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$)	0.009	0.014	0.007	0.006	0.03

β -picoline/ γ -picoline/2,4,6-collidine (0.5 ml) was sufficient to extract 100 μg of copper(II) quantitatively. Higher concentration of the reagents had no adverse effect on the extraction but was avoided due to reagent economy. Moreover, in presence of higher concentration of the reagents the absorbances of the reagent blanks become higher. Chloroform extracts showed a steady absorbance for at least 24 h.

Copper (II) was determined in presence of other diverse ions. Deviation of not more than $\pm 3\%$ from the expected absorbance was taken as the standard tolerance limit. In practice, all the pyridine bases showed similar behaviour while studying interferences. Copper(II) (48 μg) could be determined without interference in presence of 50–60 fold excess of Ni^{2+} , V^{5+} , Pt^{4+} , Rh^{3+} , Ca^{2+} , Ba^{2+} and Sr^{2+} . The systems tolerated 20–25-fold excess of Cd^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Mo^{6+} , U^{6+} , La^{3+} , Al^{3+} , Th^{4+} , Be^{2+} and Mn^{2+} . High results were obtained in presence of Co^{2+} and Pd^{2+} . Hg interfered seriously. Presence of Fe^{3+} and Zr^{4+} showed low recovery of copper. Among the anions tested 10-fold excess of borate, phosphate, bromide, phthalate, iodide, acetate did not interfere. Thiocyanate, thiosulphate, EDTA, oxalate, tartrate, citrate, fluoride and ascorbate interfered.

γ -Picoline was found to be comparatively more sensitive among the pyridine bases used. With this reagent the precision and accuracy of the proposed method were tested by analysing solutions containing a known amount of copper(II) following the recommended procedure. The average of six determinations containing 48 μg of Cu^{2+} gave a value of 48.25 μg , which varies between 46.81 to 49.68 at 95% confidence limit. The standard deviation is 1.37 μg and relative mean deviation 1.8%.

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Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Platinum using Mixed-ligand Complex Formation with Pyridine, α -Picoline, β -Picoline, γ -Picoline or 2,4,6-Collidine and Iodide

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THERE are reports^{1,2} on the extraction and separation of iodide complexes of platinum metals using tributylphosphate. In our laboratory, it has been noted that iodoplatinum(IV) with pyridine or its methyl substituted derivatives, forms mixed-ligand complexes which are extractable into chloroform. These properties of the Pt-complexes suggested that further studies of the systems might lead to the development of simple spectrophotometric method for platinum. Apart from pyridine, other bases used are α -picoline, β -picoline, γ -picoline and 2,4,6-collidine.

Experimental

Spectral curves and analytical measurements were made with a Shimadzu PR1 spectrophotometer, and a ECL 5651 digital pH meter was used for the measurement of acidities of aqueous solutions.

Chloroplatinic acid (Johnson & Matthey) (1 g) was dissolved in distilled water (100 ml) followed by standardisation as elemental platinum³. A working solution (392 μg Pt/ml) was prepared by appropriate dilution. Chloroform (E. Merck), pyridine (B.D.H.), α -picoline (Riedel), β -picoline (B.D.H.), γ -picoline (Fluka) and 2,4,6-collidine (B.D.H.) were distilled before use. Potassium iodide (B.D.H.) and all other reagents used were of A.R. grade. Different buffer solutions were prepared by standard procedures.

General procedure: An aliquot containing 100–500 μg of platinum was mixed with 0.05 M aqueous potassium iodide (2 ml) and pyridine/ α -picoline/ β -picoline/ γ -picoline/collidine (0.5 ml). Volume of the final aqueous phase was made upto 10 ml with buffer solution of desired pH. The mixture was then equilibrated with chloroform (10 ml) for 30 s. The separated organic layer was poured over anhydrous sodium sulphate to remove any retained water droplets. Finally, the absorbance of the organic extract was measured at respective absorption maxima against chloroform, and platinum(IV) was determined from a previously prepared calibration curve. To test the effect of diverse ions, the respective foreign ions were added to the system before addition of the reagents.